

TEACHING - LEARNING PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract:

Learner-centered education through appropriate methodologies facilitates effective learning as teaching-learning modalities of the higher education institution are considered to be relevant for the learner group. Although it is true that diversity of learners in respect of their background, abilities and other personal attributes will influence the pace and extent of learning, learner-centered education calls for appropriate methodologies that can be used by teachers to provide a variety of learning experiences, including individual and collaborative learning. In this paper, we have analysed various strategies followed like planning and organising the teaching- learning - evaluation schedules, support structures and systems available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students to make learning more student-centric, institutional strategy to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students to transform them into life-long learners and innovators, the technologies and facilities available and used by the faculty for effective teaching. Opportunities given to the students and faculty to advance the level of knowledge and skills, academic, personal and psycho-social support and guidance services provided to students, details of innovative teaching approaches/methods adopted by the faculty during the last four years and the efforts made by the institution to encourage the faculty to adopt new and innovative approaches and the impact of such innovative practices on student learning are also discussed.

Index Terms: Teaching - Learning Process in Higher Education Institution & Quality in Higher Education

1. Introduction:

Higher education in India particularly is institutionalized, characterized by higher concentration of importance and leadership for teachers and lesser degree of autonomy for the students who are recipients of the knowledge. This has been a stumbling block to learning among the younger generation in the context of changing student expectation over time, given the advancement in communication technology, changes in social and family setup and more orientation for free learning. This calls for a need to re-orient the pedagogy so as to shift the focus to more student centric learning. Although it is true that diversity of learners in respect of their background, abilities and other personal attributes will influence the pace and extent of learning, learner-centered education calls for appropriate methodologies that can be used by teachers to provide a variety of learning experiences, including individual and collaborative learning. This discussion pertains to Srinivas Institute of Management Studies (SIMS), and the educational model it has developed to impart quality higher education for undergraduate and post graduate students [1-2].

By translating the vision of imparting quality education and expanding opportunities to all the aspirants across all realms of knowledge into its mission, the institute envisages to become a centre of excellence to serve as change agent in the society by generating a pool of human resources trained in science and technology, management and social service, offering master degree programmes in Business

Management, Computer Science, Social Work and Bachelor degree in Commerce, Management and Computer Science. Various studies on innovations and quality in higher education including Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions [3], Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions [4], quality in higher education [5-6], Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution [7], Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models [8], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions [9], Effective Leadership and Governance [10], Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions [11], Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions [12], Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development [13], Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education [14], Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System [15], Societal Expectation And Institutional Accountability in Higher Education [16], Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions [17], Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library [18], Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented in Higher educational institution [19], Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training [20], Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities [21], Innovations in Private Universities [22], Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education [23], Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities [24], Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System [25], Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme [26], Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions [27], Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education [28], Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools [29], Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools [30], How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions [31], Academic Support through Information System [32], and Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses [33], Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System [34], ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education [35],) Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework [36], Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System [37], The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework [38], Educational institutions quest for service quality: customers" perspective [39], Comparative study of quality practices in higher education institutions [40], Quality in higher education-a survey [41], Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses [42] are studied and published. In this paper, we have analysed the strategies followed by Srinivas Institute of Management Studies, Mangalore in various teaching-learning processes. We tried to examine the scope and contribution of planning and organising the teaching, learning and evaluation schedules, and the role of the support structures and systems available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students to make learning more student-centric. The institutional strategy to transform them into life-long learners and innovators by nurturing critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students and the adoption of technologies and facilities used by the faculty for effective teaching, opportunities given to the students and faculty to advance the level of knowledge and skills, detail on the academic, personal and

psycho-social support and guidance services provided to students, innovative teaching approaches/methods adopted by the faculty are also discussed.

2. Planning and Organising the Teaching, Learning and Evaluation Schedules:

Teaching, learning and evaluation schedules are routinely prepared and implemented to facilitate teaching learning process.

Academic Calendar: This is prepared at the beginning of every academic year by the course Co-ordinators in consultation with the Head of the Institution. The calendar reflects major events, programmes and activities to be taken up in a given time frame. The calendar specifically reflects preparation of time table, allocation of subjects to various faculty, periodic faculty meetings, internal examinations, seminar presentations, assignments due date, monthly attendance status. guest lectures, industrial visits, fest & other events, projects, workshops, certificate programmes, study tour, forum & social service activities, preparatory exams, staff appraisal & student feedback, counselling for slow learners, placement training, college magazine, sports day, annual day, and graduation day celebrations.

Teaching Plan: The institution has a unique practice of distributing individual copies of the teaching plan booklet subject wise to all the students on the very day of commencement of the semester classes. The special features of the teaching plan are the following:

- ✓ The teaching plan is prepared according to the prescribed syllabus.
- ✓ It is prepared session wise so as to follow the specific number of working hours to be thought.
- ✓ The instructor who handles each subject is specified in the teaching plan.
- ✓ A copy of the time-table is also included in the teaching plan.
- ✓ Assignments and student presentation schedules are mentioned in the teaching plan.
- ✓ Business case studies/ video presentation sessions are also mentioned.
- ✓ Beyond syllabus, a value added chapter is added in each subject.
- ✓ The distribution of marks for calculating the internal assessment is also worked out in the teaching plan.
- ✓ Important references for various subjects are also included.
- ✓ In case of under-graduate programme, the discipline to be followed in campus & surroundings is also mentioned.

In accordance with transparency in academic processes, the teaching plan for all the courses are appearing in the website for reference by interested parents/persons.

Evaluation Blue Print: Evaluation blue print is prepared in every subject for Internal exams as well as University exams. Such blueprints for the last 5-10 years are merged in the Study materials provided to the students. The old question papers are available in library for student reference both in hard copy and soft copy format. Old question papers also can be downloaded from college website.

College Calendar: The institution provides a brief handbook in the form of calendar at the beginning of every Academic year to all the students of college. Salient features of the Calendar are the following:

- ✓ It contains Vision, Mission, Objectives and brief History of the college.
- ✓ It also contains information about Founder and administration of the college.
- ✓ The calendar is prepared separately for undergraduate courses as well as different Postgraduate courses.
- ✓ The Calendar contains a table on the various subjects to be studied in each semester.

- ✓ The list of elective subjects is separately provided in each course,
- ✓ The calendar also contain detailed information on Choice based Credit system and scheme of examination of the University.
- ✓ The Rules and Regulations to be followed in the college such as timings, discipline, attendance, conduct & behavior etc. are mentioned.
- ✓ Rules regarding use of library facility, registering for the exams, Internal assessments, valuation of answer scripts, practical exams, project works, pass marks in each course, improvement in exams, carryover, calculation of results are given.
- ✓ A list of teaching faculty with their qualification is given department wise.
- ✓ A list of staff members in library and office are also given for students reference.
- ✓ The list holidays followed by the college is included.
- ✓ The value added programmes such as Certificate courses, Workshops and other Training programs are also mentioned in the calendar.

Evaluation Schedule: The computerized system of evaluation followed gives early results. The affiliating University has put in place a computer aided mechanism to identify the students through bar-coded answer scripts. The examination process and the results conveyed through marks cards have undergone computer aided reforms. The students of undergraduate courses have provision for re-totalling and re-valuation system so as to improve the result and ensure justice.

3. Contribution of IQAC to Improve the Teaching-Learning Process:

The following are the contributions of Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC) to improve the teaching-learning process based on three activities:

Providing Service:

- ✓ Distribution of College Calendar & Teaching Plan
- ✓ Providing Printed Study materials in each subject as per University Syllabus.
- ✓ Quality of teaching
- ✓ Use of teaching aides
- ✓ Periodic Assessments
- ✓ Time bound Assignments
- ✓ Review of Attendance
- ✓ Parent – Teacher Communication
- ✓ Counseling & Mentoring
- ✓ Additional Classes & Open book Test Papers
- ✓ Concurrent monitoring of classes through spot checking & Video monitoring
- ✓ Value addition chapters/topics in all subjects.

Collecting Feedback:

- ✓ Student feedback on teacher assessment is collected on following parameters :
 - Competency in the subject concerned
 - Preparation for the Classes
 - Regularity in conducting classes
 - Time -consciousness
 - Syllabus completion in time
 - Presentation skill (Voice, Language, Clarity)
 - Methodology in Teaching
 - Interaction with the students
 - Accessibility to the students outside the class
 - Quality & understandability of Study Materials

- ✓ Besides, student feedback on general matters is collected through grievance cell, suggestion box, open door policy to meet the head of the institution and feedback through course co-ordinator.
- ✓ Parent's feedback is obtained on various communications from college such as SMS on Attendance & SMS on internal marks & student discipline in the campus.
- ✓ Social networking sites are also taken positively as avenues for student feedback.
- ✓ Feedback through CCD Camera fitted in all classrooms for surveillance is recorded & monitored.

Improving Service Based on Feedback:

- ✓ Faculty meetings include topics of relevance based on student feedback
- ✓ Appraisal of classroom situation by Course Coordinator/ Principal visiting classes periodically.
- ✓ The college regularly monitors face book postings and takes corrective actions in genuine cases.

4. Support Structures to Teachers:

The various support structures and systems available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students make learning more student-centric.

- ✓ Entry test and summarization are adopted as best practice to capture students attention in the class by recalling the learning's from the earlier class and concluding the learning's in the present.
- ✓ Most classes are participatory beginning with brain storming to introduce the subject and fix the context.
- ✓ Students are encouraged to express their doubts without fright or hesitation.
- ✓ Real life examples of leaders, companies and cases are made use of.
- ✓ Books are reviewed and habit of advanced reading is cultivated among the students.
- ✓ Professional newspapers in business areas namely "Hindu Business Line /Economic Times" is subscribed and made use of by all students in management courses.
- ✓ Assignment and student presentation are obligatory for students in all subjects.
- ✓ Lecturing is the primary method of teaching and LCD is fitted in all classrooms and used for teaching.
- ✓ The institution provides interactive learning among the students. This is often assisted by invited resource persons. Also talks and discourses are organized. Company managers are invited to give guest lectures and share experience.
- ✓ Project based learning is a part of all the professional courses offered by the college. The project duration varies for different courses and most of the project reports are placed before the University for valuation and grading. Best project of the year is merited through prizes.
- ✓ Computer assisted learning like simulations, experiential learning and seminars are frequently arranged to facilitate teaching-learning process.
- ✓ Video lectures of eminent persons are shown to cultivate high standards.

The following supportive structures and systems are available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students:

Structures:

- ✓ Conference room
- ✓ Library seating's

- ✓ Staff cabins
- ✓ Wi-Fi- Internet
- ✓ Computer Lab
- ✓ LCD & Video CD's
- ✓ Laptop computers as teaching information sharing gadgets

Systems:

- ✓ Group discussions
- ✓ Group Projects
- ✓ Team Assignments
- ✓ Team field work Practicum
- ✓ Organizing annual programs like Magma, Manthana, Manegma, Matrix, etc.
- ✓ Business News Paper Analysis in Groups

Strategies to nurture critical thinking, creativity and scientific temper among the students is undertaken to transform them into life-long learners and innovators in the following ways:

- ✓ Organizing and participating in programmes such as debates, competitions, and creative exhibitions, participating in competitions organized by other colleges etc.
- ✓ Students are also trained and guided in taking various competitive exams or entry into higher studies to specialize in chosen field etc.
- ✓ The pedagogy incorporates brainstorming sessions, entry test and recapitulations.
- ✓ Research projects are guided by the faculty in all courses. Original contributions are encouraged for presenting in conferences conducted by the institute for publication.
- ✓ EDP cell – The institution has a well developed entrepreneurship development cell. It conducts various activities to create awareness about entrepreneurship and to enhance the entrepreneurship skills among the students. The cell also conducts real time workshops where students get an opportunity to meet and interact with entrepreneurs and understand the real life problems. The students also get to discuss their business plans and make improvisations as per the recommendations given by the experts.
- ✓ Internship and Project Committee – This committee encourages students to come up with ideas to have real time analysis of the problems at their area of study or industry. This will be done as a value addition for students' dissertation and internship work. It supports the students to develop case studies from their project work. It guides the students to develop model and solutions for the real time problems facing by the system or industry.
- ✓ The students in computer science courses have mandatory software projects to do in a team. The best performing team is recognized and rewarded.
- ✓ The finance specialization students in business administration courses of the college conduct mock/virtual investment in share market. Based on one year monitoring, the best performance team will be rewarded.
- ✓ Some of the Institutional Certificate programmes and workshops are identified and designed in such a way that students become life-long learners and contributes to the society through their innovations.
- ✓ The faculty members are constantly in the pursuit of upgrading themselves through acquiring additional qualification which inspire the students to become life-long learners.

- ✓ The Opportunity given by way of encouraging subscription of news papers such as economic times and business line inculcate the habit of continued learners as long as they remain in the profession.

5. Usage of Technologies and Facilities:

The internet facility is provided in the campus through Wi-fi facility and networked computer labs. All classrooms are fitted with LCD projectors. Online classes are conducted using internet through wi-Fi.

LCD Projectors in Each Class: All the classrooms are fitted with LCD projectors. Faculty members use power point presentations to make classroom teaching more effective.

Audio Visual Aids: Audio Visual Aids are available in all the classrooms. Faculties are using video case studies, Movie clippings on management concepts, short films, and advertisements to explain certain topics more effectively.

WI-Fi Campus: The campus is WI-fi enabled and has high Speed internet connectivity all the time. The faculty members are using internet facility to show real time information on industry, market and economy to the students in the class rooms.

Computer Labs : Computer labs used to make students to work on applications or internet for sourcing information.

TV: Television is installed in the college. Channels like Business news are played during the working hours. This will help the students to update themselves on the issues.

Digital Library: The faculty gives assignments, which would require students to use the digital library. The digital library enables the students to get research reports, case studies and any other relevant information required to complete the given assignments.

Public Address System: The classrooms & Auditorium are equipped with the public address system. Each classroom has a hand mike, collar mike and speakers. This helps the students and faculty members in their presentations, events like subject quiz and interactions in the classroom.

Surveillance Camera based Monitoring in the Campus: The centralized surveillance facility through fixed cameras in all classrooms give real time as well as recorded discipline in the class which helps monitoring for effective teaching.

Internet Based Library Services: The faculty members can avail various internet based library services such as accessing various journals, Industry and research databases, other services from Delnet, EBSCO, etc. and internal library resource facilities which are linked to the institutional website.

National Mission on Education Through Information and Communication Technology (NME-ICT): The faculty members are also availing information and services provided by National Mission on Education through Information and Communication Technology to prepare their study materials, lectures, and for advanced information.

High Speed Printers & Scanners Facility: Although sparingly used, the high speed printers and scanners are help the faculty to prepare multiple copies of case studies, business game etc.

NPTEL Video Lectures: The College is encouraging to watch NPTEL video lecturers of IIT professors in the area of Computer Science, Business Management and Social Science by downloading such videos and issuing the CD's of such lectures by college library.

Virtual Lab: Through simulation in virtual lab, e-learning is enhanced.

Digital Camera & Videography Facility: Through digital videography the classroom presentations are replayed to serve as feedback for improved learning.

Open Educational Resources:

- ✓ Training of usage of Open Courseware by MIT & Sloan School of Business, IIM's, IIT's, IISC & IIIT's.
- ✓ Training & usage of Open Source Software from AICTE websites.
- ✓ Training on finding & usage of case studies from various free sources.
- ✓ Training on online Job hunting through online job service providers.
- ✓ Training on finding & usage of online text books from various websites.
- ✓ Training on finding & usage of edX consortium online courses

Mobile Education: The College takes the faculty to the community/ industry as a part of learning through mobile education. Some of the Faculty Development Programs are conducted outside the college to enhance the effectiveness of training.

6. Opportunities Given to the Students and Faculty:

Students:

- ✓ **Seminars** - The college conducts seminars, symposium and conferences periodically and students are encouraged to participate in these events. Students are also encouraged to participate in such programmes conducted by other institutions.
- ✓ **Workshops** - The Institute organizes several workshops.
- ✓ **Guest Lecture** - the Institute invites the experts from industry & NGO to deliver the lectures on various ongoing issues and current happenings in the corporate world/Community to provide real time information and knowledge to the students.
- ✓ **Blended Learning** - In addition to chalk and talk method of teaching, the faculty members are using the IT enabled learning tools such as PPT, Video clippings, Audio system, online sources, Simulation software, communication lab and decision making games and field work conference to expose the students to combine advanced knowledge with practical learning.
- ✓ **Certificate Programmes:** A list of Certificate programmes along with the duration, goals and objectives.
- ✓ **Research Based Projects:** All courses of our college offers research based projects through undertaking dissertation through guided supervision.
- ✓ **Practical Assignments:** Assignments are required to be submitted by the students on various topics which are within the curriculum. This is also counted for calculating internal assessment marks.

Faculty:

To enhance the knowledge and skills of the faculty members, the Institute frequently organizes FDPs, MDPs, Workshops and training programmes on teaching pedagogy, general management and subject related topics. The Institute encourages and deposes the faculty members to seminars, conferences, workshops, FDPs and other developmental programmes organized by other Institutes and university to get exposure.

7. Details of Academic, Personal, and Psycho-Social Support:

Detail on the academic, personal and psycho-social support and guidance services (professional counseling/mentoring/academic advice) provided to students are:

Academic Support:

- ✓ Academic Support through Study Materials benefits all the students undergoing

various courses in the college.

- ✓ Academic Support through Mentoring is provided to weak students in respective subjects by the concerned faculty and a record of the progress is maintained for continuous monitoring.
- ✓ Academic Advice through Course Co-ordinators every week helps to unwind student pressure from curriculum demands.
- ✓ Academic Advice by Principal visiting the class at least once in every month helps to motivate students towards studies and helps to maintain discipline in the college.

Personal Support:

- ✓ Individual Monitoring focus on erratic behavior in the classroom or college premises.
- ✓ Health guidance is provided by Campus medical Officer
- ✓ Financial support through Bank Loan is arranged.
- ✓ Job opportunities are intimated and assisted to seek Placement
- ✓ Attendance shortage and continued absence is intimated periodically to home/parents through SMS.

Psycho-Social Support:

- ✓ Psycho-social support is provided to the students through Counseling.

8. Details of Innovative Teaching Approaches/Methods Adopted:

The various teaching –learning methods adopted in our Institute are:

Project Based Teaching: Faculty members give minor projects to group of students in different courses. On the completion of the projects, the team has to present the same and the faculty will award suitable marks/grades.

Lab Based Teaching: The Institute also has three computer labs with internet facility. The students are taken to the lab by the faculty members to provide them real time information on subjects.

Experiential Learning: To improve the understanding of the subject case studies are framed jointly by faculty and students recalling their experience during visits and observations. This includes managerial styles, superior and subordinate relationship, interpersonal communication, problem solving etc. For this purpose the students are sent on short-term assignments to the industry to have practical experience on working of industry.

Theatre Based Learning: The students are required to enact / explain certain concept through theater performance like role play, drama or short play on the assigned topics. Street plays are enacted in public locations to create awareness on social issues.

Simulation Games: To give a real time experience of the business problems, simulation games are played in the classrooms. Students get a real feel of decision making, problem analysis and problem solving.

Video Case Study: Faculties assigned students with special projects like making video case studies on specific topics.

Activity Based Learning: Students are involved in various activities and management games related to the topics from the subject.

Technology Based Learning: The internet, LCD, different application software etc. enables technology based learning.

Learning from Nature & Environment: Rural camp conducted for the students of social work and National Service Scheme are meant to learn from nature and environment.

Community Based Learning: Various activities conducted in the communities for MSW

students and the activities conducted by the College NGO by name SIRRA provides community based learning.

Field Work Based Learning: MSW course require specific number of field work practicum as part of the curriculum. This is meant to sensitize the social work students to social issues.

Analytical Learning: Quantitative techniques of analysis are used in learning mostly by MCA students and also by finance specialization students of MBA.

Team Based Learning: The sum of individual performance is always less than team's performance. Hence in software development team based learning is made use of.

Observation Based Learning: Demonstrations such as role play facilitates observation based learning.

Social Service Based Learning: Community interactions help, build and develop interpersonal relationship through which social service is channelized.

9. Usage of Library Resources to Augment the Teaching-Learning Process:

The library is stocked with subject related books, general management books, personality development books, books on competitive examinations, encyclopedias, National and International Journals, Magazines, newspapers both English and local language, CD and research reports. The institution also has digital library with access to journals through online data base like Delnet, EBSCO and JGATE. These resources are used in the following ways:

Library Hour: One hour per week is designated as library hour in the timetable for P.G. Programs. The faculty members in-charge for the library hours introduce the students to various facilities available in the library databases from various websites to help students get in-depth information and knowledge about subjects taught in the class room. Business Management students are motivated by the faculty members to understand industry and market trends through publications, newspapers, journals and other available resources during the library hour. Publications and journals are available for reference during library hour for other courses.

Library Based Projects and Assignments: The faculty members help students designs projects and assignments for which the students are required to refer to the resources available in the library.

Simulated Learning Through Digital Library: MBA Students are exposed to the stock market operations and trading through simulated online games available with the digital library of the college.

Library Based Research Work: Students are exposed to various sources of online information and instructed to carry out the fundamental and technical analysis practically.

Faculty: The faculty members are extensively using the library and the digital library for class preparation and for research purposes. The faculty also refers the collection of business case studies for their class room discussions.

Library Information Through College Website: The library provides old question papers as well as study materials of concerned subjects through college website so that students and faculty members can access them from their home whenever required. Students and faculty members can also find availability of textbooks and project reports subject wise by sitting in home through subject wise textbook list available in the college website.

Collection of Educational CD's & NPTEL Learning Resources: The library has vast collection of Soft-skill based CD's and Subject wise NPTEL video lecture CD's for student reference. Students can also copy these resources in their laptop/pen drive.

Collection of IIM Study Materials: The College has procured ample number of Study materials from IIM (Ahmadabad) in order to sensitize the students with resources of reputed B-Schools.

Collection of Project Reports: The library maintains vast collection of project reports in all UG & PG programmes. These reports are available for students to refer at the time of planning their projects.

Availability of Digitized Textbooks for Students: Rare and expensive books are available in digitized form with the library and made available for the users for internal usage based on request.

Book Exhibition: Library organizes book exhibitions of various publishers for limited duration round the year where students and faculty can suggest new books to be procured and added to the collection of books in the library.

10. Challenges to Complete the Curriculum Within the Planned Time:

Major challenges in completing the curriculum within the planned time frame has been very unusual. However, the following precautions are taken for any deviations from the time frame:

Technology Based Learning: Through promoting the use of LCD projectors in classrooms lot of time could be saved than otherwise.

Teaching Plan: This is a tool for dividing the entire syllabus in to practical classroom sessions which could anticipate the required number of classes beforehand so as to prepare students for the examination.

College Calendar: It creates an impact of time limits available for learning so that pace of the teaching is adjusted accordingly.

Study Materials: The lucidity of narration in the study material makes learning comfortable and easy for the students and to cope with time constraints.

Additional Classes: In case required, additional classes are also conducted to compensate any loss of time.

Expertise of the Faculty: The faculty are competent and experienced enough to handle such situations to complete the syllabus in time.

11. The Institutional Effort to Monitor and Evaluate the Quality of Teaching-Learning:

Regular Conduct of Internal Examinations: Internal examinations are conducted for all the courses at regular intervals as planned in the academic calendar which is prepared by the HOD in consultation with the academic faculty at the beginning of the calendar year/semester.

Result Analysis: The results of the University examinations are analysed through segregating percentage of students in terms of achievements as reflected in their marks scored in each examination. The faculty who has been engaging classes for the concerned subjects will be responsible for the poor performance of the students.

Feedback from Students: The College collects feedback from students in a proper format at the end of every semester and is reviewed by the principal. This feedback is also conveyed to the concerned faculty for rectification and improvement.

Class Visits of Head of the Department and Principal: A direct and first hand appraisal of the classes is obtained by the HOD/Principal periodically while the classes are in progress.

Training of New Faculty: New faculty members are provided opportunity to attend the classes of experienced faculty in order to develop competency in teaching process.

IQAC: IQAC closely monitors and evaluate the quality of teaching- learning processes in the college.

CCD Monitoring of the Classes: The college one of the beginners in using high technology to maintain discipline as well as ensure the regular classes to the students through the closed circuit Cameras.

Students Opinion Through Suggestion Box: Students who hesitate to open-up in other forums can make use of the suggestion box inter alia the quality of teaching of the various subjects.

End User Benefits Documentation: Through a new practice of monitoring the classes in progress, by visiting the classes during every hour and recording the signature of faculty in the classes ensures that the end users are benefitted.

12. Conclusion:

Teaching-learning process in higher education institution integrates planning and organizing schedules, put in place support system and structures, usage of technologies and facilities, provision of growth opportunities, devising innovative teaching approaches, personal and psycho-social support, and augmentation of resources. The support structures and systems available for teachers to develop skills like interactive learning, collaborative learning and independent learning among the students are intended to make learning more students centric. The use of technology makes learning effective. The case of Srinivas Institute of management Studies is a glaring instance of appropriate use of these elements. Monitoring the benefit is manifold. Most significant in assessing the efficacy of improved teaching – learning process is the output analysis, although process analysis, feedback analysis and quality review analysis are to be taken in combination.

13. References:

1. Manual for self-study report of affiliated colleges. National Assessment and Accreditation Council. June 2013.
2. Hill, Y., Lomas, L., Mac Gregor, J., Students perceptions of quality in higher education. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 11, No. 1, pp. 15-20, 2003.
3. Srinivas Rao A., Suresh Kumar P. M., & Aithal P. S., Strategic Planning in Higher Education Institutions : A Case Study of SIMS - VISION 2025, *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*; Vol.5 Issue 2, pp. 29-42, April 30, 2015.
4. Aithal P. S., Srinivas Rao A., & Suresh Kumar P. M., How Innovations and Best Practices can Transform Higher Education Institutions: A case study of SIMS, *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, Vol. 6, Issue 2, pp.83 - 98, 2015.
5. Gopal K. Kanji, Abdul Malek Bin A. Tambi & William Wallace, A comparative study of quality practices in higher education institutions in the US and Malaysia, *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 10, Issue 3, pp. 357-371, 1999.
6. Mohammad S. Owlia, Quality in higher education-a survey, *Total Quality Management* Vol. 7, Issue 2, pp. 161-172, 1996.
7. Aithal P.S., Internal Quality Assurance Cell and its Contribution to Quality Improvement in Higher Education Institutions : A Case of SIMS, *GE International Journal of Management Research (IJMR)*, Vol. 3, Issue 5, May 2015 pp. 70-83.
8. Aithal P. S., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Enhancement of Graduate attributes in Higher Education Institutions through Stage Models, *IMPACT: International Journal of Research in Business Management*, Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 121 - 130, March 2015.
9. Aithal P. S., Srinivas Rao A., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions : A case study of SIMS, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 18-31, May 2015.

10. Aithal P. S., How an Effective Leadership and Governance Supports to Achieve Institutional Vision, Mission, and Objectives, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 5, pp. 154-161, May 2015.
11. Aithal P. S., Strategy Development and Deployment in Higher Education Institutions, *Elixir International Journal*, Vol. 84, pp. 33594 – 33597, 2015.
12. Aithal P. S., Faculty Empowerment Strategies in Higher Education Institutions. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 108-115, July 2015.
13. Aithal P. S., MBA++ as a Unique & Successful Model in Integrated Development of Business Executives. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 124-133, July 2015.
14. Aithal P. S. and Suresh Kumar P. M., Applying SWOC Analysis to an Institution of Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 231-247, July 2015.
15. Aithal P. S. and Sridhar Acharya P., Techniques for Electric Energy Auditing in Education System. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 318-325, July 2015.
16. Aithal P. S., Suresh Kumar P. M. and Deekshitha, Societal Expectation and Institutional Accountability in Higher Education. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 361-373, July 2015.
17. Aithal P. S., Suresh Kumar P. M. and Pavithra Kumari, Methods and Approaches for Employability Skill Generation in Higher Educational Institutions. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 390-410, July 2015.
18. Aithal P. S. and Harischandra P., Quality Enhancement in Higher Education Institutions through Best Practices in Library: A Case of SIMS. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 489-505, July 2015.
19. Reshma, Shailashree V. T, Sridhar Acharya P., and Aithal P. S., Analysis of Academic Administrative System Implemented at SIMS. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 5, Issue 7, pp. 771-787, July 2015.
20. Pradeep M.D, and Aithal P. S., Learning through Team Centric Exercise & Key Point Pedagogy - An effective Learning Model for Slow Learners in Higher Education Training, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development*, Vol. 2, Issue 9, pp. 265-270, September, 2015.
21. Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar P. M., Opportunities and Challenges for Private Universities in India, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 88-113, January 2016.
22. Aithal P. S., & Suresh Kumar P.M., Innovations in Private Universities : A Case of Srinivas University, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 250-264, January 2016.
23. Aithal P. S., Creating Innovators through setting up organizational Vision, Mission and Core Values : a Strategic Model in Higher Education, *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE)*, Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 310-324, January 2016.
24. Aithal, P.S., Comparative Study on MBA Programmes in Private & Public Universities - A case study of MBA programme plan of Srinivas University,

- International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR) , Vol. 4, Issue 12, pp. 106-122, 2015.
25. Aithal P. S. & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, Impact of On-line Education on Higher Education System, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME) (www.rdmodernresearch.com) Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 225-235, 2016.
 26. Aithal P. S. & Jeevan Pinto, Innovations in Higher Education - A new model implemented in MCA degree programme of Srinivas University, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME) (www.rdmodernresearch.com) Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 275-289, 2016.
 27. Sridhar Acharya P. and Aithal P. S., Environmental Consciousness in Higher Educational Institutions : A case of SIMS, International Journal of Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp. 273-284, 2016.
 28. Aithal P. S., and Suresh Kumar P.M., Analysis of Choice Based Credit System in Higher Education, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), Volume I, Issue I, pp. 278-284, 2016.
 29. Aithal P. S., Innovations in Student Centric Learning – A Study of Top Business Schools in India, International Journal of Engineering Research and Modern Education (IJERME), Volume I, Issue I, pp. 298-306, 2016.
 30. Aithal P. S., Innovations in Experimental Learning – A Study of World Top Business Schools, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.360-375, 2016.
 31. Aithal P. S., How to Increase Research Productivity in Higher Educational Institutions –SIMS Model, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.447-458, 2016.
 32. Aithal P. S. & Suresh Kumar P. M., Academic Support through Information System: Srinivas Integrated Model, International Journal of Scientific Research and Modern Education (IJSRME), Vol. I, Issue I, pp.376-384, 2016.
 33. Line Wittek, Laurence Habib, Laurence Habib, Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses, International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, Vol. 25, Number 3, pp.275-287, 2013.
 34. Aithal P.S., & Shubhrajyotsna Aithal, An Innovative Education Model to realize Ideal Education System, International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp. 2464 - 2469, March, 2015.
 35. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., ABCD analysis of Stage Model in Higher Education, International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), Vol. 6, Issue 1, pp. 11-24, January 2016.
 36. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., Analysis of NAAC Accreditation System using ABCD framework, International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering (IJMIE), Volume 6, Issue 1, pp.30 - 44, (January 2016).
 37. Aithal P.S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P. M., Application of ABCD Analysis Framework on Private University System in India, International Journal of Management Sciences and Business Research (IJMSBR), Vol. 5, Issue 4, pp. 159-170, April 2016.
 38. Aithal P. S., Shailashree V.T., & Suresh Kumar P.M., The Study of New National Institutional Ranking System using ABCD Framework, International Journal of

Current Research and Modern Education (IJCRME), Volume I, Issue I, pp. 389 – 402, 2016.

39. Joseph, M., Yakhou, M., Stone, G., An educational institution:s quest for service quality: customers“ perspective. *Quality Assurance in Education*, Vol. 13 No. 1, pp. 66-82, 2005.
40. Gopal K. Kanji, Abdul Malek Bin A. Tambi & William Wallace, A comparative study of quality practices in higher education institutions in the US and Malaysia, *Total Quality Management*, Vol. 10, Issue 3, pages 357-371, 1999.
41. Mohammad S. Owlia, Quality in higher education-a survey, *Total Quality Management* Vol. 7, Issue 2, pages 161-172, 1996.
42. Line Wittek, Laurence Habib, Laurence Habib, Quality Teaching and Learning as Practice Within Different Disciplinary Discourses, *International Journal of Teaching and Learning in Higher Education*, Vol. 25, Number 3, pp.275-287, 2013.